

Library Carpentry: Konzepte und Community

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- Themen: Medizin, Gesundheit, Biologie, Agrarwissenschaften, Ernährungswissenschaften, Umweltwissenschaften
- Etwa 120 MitarbeiterInnen
- Zwei Standorte: Köln und Bonn
- Seit Mai 2018 zahlreiche Forschungsaktivitäten

Cost per Genome

A red Swiss Army knife is shown with several tools extended, including a large blade, a pair of pliers, a corkscrew, and a saw. The knife is resting on a wooden surface. A semi-transparent white box is overlaid on the center of the image, containing text.

Bibliotheken können durch Forschungsdatenmanagement und Informationsdienstleistungen helfen, Forschung besser zu gestalten.

Es gibt eine signifikante Lücke zwischen dem Bedarf an nötigen und vorhandenen Fähigkeiten bei BibliothekarInnen.

Caution
Gap

Shifting to Data Savvy: The Future of Data Science In Libraries

Burton, Matt and Lyon, Liz and Erdmann, Chris and Tijerina, Bonnie (2018)

Software and data skills for
people working in library- and
information-related roles

What we do

Library Carpentry develops lessons and teaches workshops for and with people working in library- and information-related roles. Our goal is to create an on-ramp to empower this community to use software and data in their own work as well as be advocates for and train others in efficient, effective and reproducible data and software practices. Our workshops are based on **our lessons**. Workshop hosts, Instructors, and learners must be prepared to follow The Carpentries **Code of Conduct**.

[More ▾](#)

Who we are

We are a diverse, global community of volunteer **Instructors**, helpers, and Maintainers. Library Carpentry is guided by an **interim governance group** and a **curriculum advisory committee**. **Our audience** are primarily people working in library- and information-related roles.

[More ▾](#)

Get involved

See all the **ways you can engage** and **get involved** with Library Carpentry. Follow us on **Twitter**.

[More ▾](#)

<https://librarycarpentry.org/>

We teach foundational coding
and data science skills to
researchers worldwide.

What we do

Who we are

Get involved

Teaching basic lab skills
for research computing

Our Workshops ›
Find or host a workshop.

Our Lessons ›
Have a look at what we teach.

Get Involved ›
Help us help researchers.

Upcoming Workshops

Click on an individual event to learn more about that event, including contact information and registration instructions.

Max Planck Institute for Evolutionary Anthropology Instructors: Bret Alexander Beheim, Han Tran Helpers: Ilaria Pretelli	Nov 23 - Nov 27, 2020	
Research Software London Instructors: Christopher Cave-Ayland, Iain Barras Helpers: Jazz Mack Smith, Jeremy Cohen, Tony Yang, Jay DesLauriers, Matt Alexandrakis	Nov 25 - Nov 27, 2020	
December 2020 SWC Workshop @TU Delft (online) Instructors: Nicole Dijkstra	Dec 1 - Dec 9, 2020	

DATA CARPENTRY

BUILDING COMMUNITIES TEACHING UNIVERSAL DATA LITERACY

Data Carpentry develops and teaches workshops on the fundamental data skills needed to conduct research. Our mission is to provide researchers high-quality, domain-specific training covering the full lifecycle of data-driven research. Data Carpentry is now a lesson project within The Carpentries, having merged with Software Carpentry in January, 2018. Data Carpentry's focus is on the introductory computational skills needed for data management and analysis in all domains of research. Our lessons are domain-specific, and build on the existing knowledge of learners to enable them to quickly apply skills learned to their own research. *Our initial target audience is learners who have little to no prior computational experience.* We create a friendly environment for learning to empower researchers and enable data driven discovery.

A VERY BRIEF HISTORY OF

THE CARPENTRIES

- Weitestgehend durch Freiwillige betrieben
- Globale, offene Community
- Train-the-Trainer-Konzept
- Materialien werden von der Carpentry Gemeinschaft als OER entwickelt (mit jeweils 3+ Maintainern)
- Regelmäßige Calls (Pre-/Post-Workshop – Mentoring Subcommittee debriefing)
- Evidenzbasierte Lehrmethoden
- Feedback, Feedback, Feedback

- Gebühr für organisierte Workshops
- Mitgliedschaft von Organisationen
- Spenden

”Library Carpentry develops lessons and teaches workshops for and with people working in library- and information-related roles. Our goal is to create an on-ramp to empower this community to use software and data in their own work as well as be advocates for and train others in efficient, effective and reproducible data and software practices.”

- Erlernen von Konzepten und Vokabular der Softwareentwicklung und Datenwissenschaften sowie Anwendung dieser im Bibliothekskontext
- Identifikation und Anwendung von guter Praxis im Umgang mit Daten
- Lernen wie mittels Programmen, Daten transformiert werden können
- Schaffung eines besseren Verständnisses von KollegenInnen aus Forschung und IT-Bereich
- Automatisierung von repetitiven und fehleranfälligen Aufgaben

- 2 Tage
- 10 - 20 TeilnehmerInnen
- Mind. 2 InstruktorInnen (mind. 1 zertifiziert)
- Etwa 2 Helfende
- "Live-Coding"
- Niederschwellig und interaktiv
- Feedback! (Pre-/Post-Workshop survey; Rückmeldungen nach jeder Lehreinheit)

Our Core Curriculum

Our Core Curriculum consists of the lessons in the table below. These have been taught many times, and have been further refined after instructor and learner feedback. For more information regarding core lessons and workshops, see **Our Workshops** and the **Workshop Overview**.

The lessons introduce terms, phrases, and concepts in software development and data science, how to best work with data structures, and use regular expressions in finding and matching data. We introduce the Unix-style command line interface, and teach basic shell navigation, as well as the use of loops and pipes for linking shell commands. We also introduce `grep` for searching and subsetting data across files. Exercises cover the counting and mining of data. In addition, we cover working with OpenRefine to transform and clean data, and the benefits of working collaboratively via Git/GitHub and using version control to track your work.

Lessons

Lesson	Site	Repository	Reference	Instructor Notes	Status	Maintainer(s)
Workshop Overview		Stable	Shari Laster*, Carmi Cronje, Paul R. Pival, Anton Angelo (Past Maintainer: James Baker, Chris Erdmann)			
Introduction to Working with Data (Regular Expressions)		Stable	Shari Laster*, Carmi Cronje, Paul R. Pival, Anton Angelo (Past Maintainers: James Baker, Chris Erdmann)			
The UNIX Shell		Stable	Danielle Kane*, Nilani Ganeshwaran, John Wright, Anna Oates, Tim Dennis (Past Maintainer: Belinda Weaver)			
OpenRefine		Stable	Erin Carrillo*, Owen Stephens, Paul R. Pival, Kristin Lee (Past Maintainers: Carmi Cronje, Chris Erdmann, Juliane Schneider)			
Introduction to Git		Stable	Silvia di Giorgio, Eric Lopatin, Drew Heles, Christopher Felker, Chuck McAndrew (Past Maintainers: Eva Seidlmayer, Thea Atwood, Katrin Leinweber, Belinda Weaver, Jez Cope, Chris Erdmann)			

<http://librarycarpentry.org/lessons/>

Extended Curriculum

The following Library Carpentry lessons can also be taught in addition to our core curriculum. Some of the lessons have been taught infrequently and still need further work. We would value any feedback on these lessons.

Lessons

Lesson	Site	Repository	Reference	Instructor Notes	Status	Maintainer(s)
SQL		Stable	Kristin Lee, Chris Erdmann, Lise Doucette, Jacqueline Frisina, Jesse Lambertson (Past Maintainers: Elaine Wong, Janice Chan)			
Tidy Data		Stable	Sherry Lake*, Tim Dennis, Thea Atwood, Erika Mias (Past Maintainer: Jez Cope)			
Webscraping		Alpha	Joshua Dull*, Thomas Guignard (Past Maintainer: Belinda Weaver)			
Introduction to Python		Alpha	Elizabeth Wickes*, Laura Wrubel, Konrad Foerstner, Drew Heles (Past Maintainers: Carlos Martinez, Richard Vankoningsveld)			
Introduction to Data for Archivists		Alpha	Katherine Koziar*, Jeanine Finn, and Scott Peterson (Past Maintainers: Jenny Bunn, Noah Geraci, and James Baker)			
Introduction to R		Alpha	Clarke Iakovakis*, John Little, Stéphane Guillou, Tim Dennis (looking for Maintainers)			

* Indicates Lead Maintainer

Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things

The Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things are brief guides (stand alone, self paced training materials), called "Things", that can be used by the research community to understand FAIR in different contexts but also as starting points for conversations around FAIR.

Lesson	Site	Repository	About	DOI	Status	Maintainer(s)
Top 10 FAIR Data & Software Things		Beta	Liz Stokes, Chris Erdmann, Juande Santander-Vela (looking for Maintainers)			

<http://librarycarpentry.org/lessons/>

Conceptual Curriculum

The following lessons are conceptual (pre-alpha) and are currently being discussed and/or under development. Issues/pull requests are one way to see current activity but you can also reach out to the Maintainers to see where the lesson discussions/development are at.

Lessons

Lesson	Site	Repository	Reference	Instructor Notes	Status	Maintainer(s)
MarcEdit		Conceptual	Owen Stephens*, Jennifer Eustis, Abigail Sparling (looking for Maintainers)			
Wikidata		Conceptual	Till Sauerwein, Muhammad Elhossary, Konrad Förstner*, Rabea Müller (looking for Maintainers)			
FAIR Data & Software		Conceptual	Chris Erdmann*, Liz Stokes, Kristina Hettne, Carmi Cronje (looking for Maintainers)			
XML		Conceptual	Catherine Smith, Jesse Johnston, Phil Reed, Katrina Simone Fenlon, Nilani Ganeshwaran (looking for Maintainers)			

This lesson is still being designed and assembled (Pre-Alpha version)

Home

Code of Conduct

Setup

Episodes ▾

Extras ▾

License

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Library Carpentry Wikidata

This Library Carpentry lesson introduces librarians to Wikidata. At the conclusion of the lesson you will: know what the Wikidata interface looks like; know how Wikidata is linked to other Wiki projects; know the underlying concepts of Wikidata; create and develop Wikidata items yourself; add references to Wikidata; create a search query in Wikidata using the query language SPARQL; understand how to perform a mass import into Wikidata.

Under Design

This lesson is currently in its early design stage; please check the repository issues and pull requests to see what we have so far. Contributions are very welcome

Prerequisites

1. Learners need a proper internet connection.
2. There is no need for pre installations.

Schedule

	Setup	Download files required for the lesson
00:00	1. What is Wikidata?	What are Items and Statements? <i>How does the Wikidata interface look like?</i>

Search docs

GENERAL RESOURCES

- ASSESSMENT
- COMMUNICATION
- FOR INSTRUCTORS
- INSTRUCTOR DEVELOPMENT
- INSTRUCTOR TRAINING
- LESSON DEVELOPMENT
- LESSON MAINTENANCE
- POLICIES
- REGIONAL COMMUNITIES
- TEACHING AND HOSTING
- WORKSHOP ADMINISTRATION
- GOVERNANCE
- ABOUT
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The Carpentries Handbook

General Resources

- ASSESSMENT
 - [Learner Assessment](#)
 - [Programmatic Assessment](#)
 - [Assessment Network](#)
- COMMUNICATION
 - [Getting your news out there](#)
 - [Submitting blog posts](#)
 - [Newsletter](#)
 - [Slack and Mailing Lists](#)
 - [Carpentries Commons](#)
 - [Presentations](#)
 - [Scheduling Online Community Events](#)
- FOR INSTRUCTORS
 - [For Current Carpentries Instructors](#)
 - [Setting up a workshop website](#)
 - [Become a Carpentries Instructor](#)
 - [Motivation for people to train as Instructors](#)
- INSTRUCTOR DEVELOPMENT
 - [Instructor Development Committee](#)
 - [Instructor Discussion Sessions](#)
 - [Mentoring Groups](#)

The Carpentries in DACH Countries

Rabea Müller is our Regional Coordinator for DACH Countries. This includes Carpentries activity in Austria, Germany, and Switzerland. She is ready to help you with any questions you have about running Carpentries workshops or any other ways you can get involved with The Carpentries in DACH Countries. Contact her at admin-dach@carpentries.org.

Rabea Müller

Want to host a Carpentries workshop in DACH Countries? Fill out [this form](#) and we will get right back to you!

General questions about The Carpentries outside of DACH Countries? Contact team@carpentries.org and we'll get your message to the right team member to follow up.

Library Workshop besucht ... und dann?

./ HackyHour Cologne

Code|Tools|Discussion|Community

Download as .zip

Download as .tar.gz

View on GitHub

About

Come to talk about code, tools and science, in a social environment. If you have a problem in one of those areas: bring it along and get help. If you want to know how computational tools and code can improve your science or you just want to drink a coffee: join us. The HackyHour is open to all interested librarians and scientists of the Cologne area and beyond.

When and Where

Our meeting takes place on Thursdays from 2-3pm in this online [meeting room](#). In order to secure a peer to peer interaction frontal teaching longer than 15min is dispensed for HackyHour. Discussions are preferred to be held in English or English and German enable international researchers to join the meeting.

You can come without registration but feel free to join the discussion in the linked pad (see table below) if you have any questions beforehand.

Topics

In addition to the open discussions we also aim to talk about specific topics at each HackyHour. However prior knowledge or interest in these topics is not a prerequisite. Online discussions for these topics are accessible via the following links.

Date	Summary	Discussion
2020-10-08		Hacktoberfest
2020-08-27		

Ich freue mich auf ihre Fragen!

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zbmed.de / @ZB_MED

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Technology
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